

An Analysis of Pupils' Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP) Results in Selected Core Subjects: A Basis for Improved Classroom Instruction

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP) Results of the Grade-VI pupils in Banaybanay Elementary School in English, Science, and Mathematics. The descriptive-correlational design was used in this study. The researcher utilized index of difficulty, percentage, mean, and Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation.

The study revealed that majority of the pupils are female. The pupils' first grading period performance in English is in the "developing" level and in the "approaching proficiency" level for both Science and Mathematics. It further showed that the pupils' DUTP performance in English and in Science is in the "developing" level and in "approaching proficiency" level in Mathematics.

Moreover, the following proportions of items in the DUTP examinations were found to be difficult: one-fourth of the items in English, more than half of the items in Mathematics, and almost half of the items in Science.

Furthermore, there was a "high" relationship between the first grading and DUTP performance of the pupils in English as well as in Science. A "marked" relationship was also noted in Mathematics.

Lastly, a substantial difference was revealed between the performance of the male and female pupils in the following areas: English and Science in the first grading period; and English in the DUTP examination in favor of the female pupils.

The study has the following recommendations:

1. Since the pupils were in the "developing" level in English (both in the first grading and DUTP performance), the teachers should consider the item analysis results. Items that were classified as difficult should be stressed more in classroom discussion.
2. Inasmuch as there were numerous difficult items in Mathematics and Science during the DUTP examination, a well-planned tutorial session should be organized by the teachers. This activity should be done a month before the said examination.
3. The male pupils should be encouraged to participate more in classroom discussion. During class activities, they should be paired with female pupils who excel in class.
4. The supervisors should ensure that the items included in the DUTP examination go through an item analysis.

Keywords: *Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP), Core Subjects, Classroom Instruction*

I. INTRODUCTION

Different kinds of assessments are appropriate in different settings. One of the most important and authentic techniques of assessing and estimating student performance across the full domain of learning outcomes as targeted by the instructor is the classroom test. Each item on a test is intended to sample student performance on a particular learning outcome. Thus, creating valid and reliable classroom tests is very important to an instructor for assessing student performance, achievement, and success in the class. One powerful technique available to the instructors for the guidance and improvement of instruction is the test item analysis (Shakil).

Calmorin cited that item analysis does not only identify if the items are valid or reliable but it also gives useful information for class discussion and data for helping students improve their learning method (134).

The Division Unified Testing Program (DUTP) examination is a yearly division assessment given to pupils to evaluate the performance of the teachers in their field. The scores of the pupils are thereby included in the computation of their second grading performance. It is found out that the DUTP results have been very poor over the years.

In this research, the items in the DUTP questionnaires will be analyzed to clarify and identify areas that need to be stressed in classroom discussion. Through the results, possible remediation or enhancement activity can be given to the pupils to improve their performance. It is on this premise that the researcher thought of conducting this study.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher made use of the descriptive-correlational methodology of research. It was descriptive because it aims to analyze the DUTP results of the pupils in the core subjects. It was also correlational since it identified the relationship between some factors and the pupils' DUTP performance.

Research Environment

The place of the study is in Banaybanay, Bayawan City which is one of the hinterland barangays in Bayawan. Although it is 38 kilometers away from the city, Banaybanay enjoys the accessibility of electricity and water supply. There is a certain place in Banaybanay where one can access to a smart signal. This barangay is known for their motto, "BastaBanaybanay Mag Tinabangay".

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 80 Grade-VI pupils of Banaybanay Elementary School.

Research Instruments

The study made use of the first grading result and the DUTP performance of the pupils. The sets of examinations in the core subjects were used by the researcher for item analysis with the approval of the division superintendent.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result of the study and provides in-depth analysis and interpretation of data.

Table 1. Sex Profile of the Pupils

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	35	43.75
Female	45	56.25
Total	80	100

The data in Table 1 reflect that 43.75% of the pupils are male and 56.25% of them are female. This means that majority of the pupils in this study are female.

**Table 2. Performance of the Pupils in the Core Subjects during the First Grading Period
N = 80**

Rating	Verbal Description	English		Mathematics		Science	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
90% and above	Advanced	0	0	0	0	19	23.75
85% - 89%	Proficient	10	12.50	15	18.75	11	13.75
80% - 84%	Approaching Proficiency	21	26.25	59	73.75	16	20.00
75% - 79%	Developing	49	61.25	6	7.50	34	42.50
Mean Performance μ		78.68 (Developing)		82.36 (Approaching Proficiency)		82.40 (Approaching Proficiency)	
Standard Deviation σ		4.01		2.57		6.21	
Overall Mean Performance		81.15%(Approaching Proficiency)					

The data in Table 2 point out that in English, majority (61.25%) of the pupils are in the “developing” level which implies that the pupils possess only the minimum knowledge and skills and core understanding of the subject. Their overall performance is also of the same category. The study of Agor negates this finding. He revealed that his respondents are in the “approaching proficiency” level (81.41%) in English (36).

The data further reflect that in Mathematics, majority (73.75%) of the pupils are in the “approaching proficiency” level which indicates that the pupils have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understanding of the subject. Their overall performance is also of the same classification. Sapuan’s finding is in consonance of this result. Her respondents also obtained an “approaching proficiency” (80.12%) classification in Mathematics during the first grading period (46). Agor likewise had the same finding. He also discovered that the overall performance of his respondents in Mathematics is in the “approaching proficiency” (80.00%) level (36).

The data lastly indicate that in Science, only 42.50% of the pupils are in the “developing” level, 23.75% are in the “advanced” level and 20.00% are in the “approaching proficiency” level. It is good to note

that almost one-fourth of the pupils have reached the “advanced” level in Science which means that these pupils exceed the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding. Their overall performance is classified to be in the “approaching proficiency” level. Mugatar affirms this finding as he also indicated in his study that his respondents obtained an overall classification of “approaching proficiency”(44). Agor, on the other hand, also indicated the same. His respondents acquired an “approaching proficiency” (80.71%) category in Science (36).

Synthesizing the results, the researcher finds out that the pupils are in the “developing” level in English and are in the “approaching proficiency” level in Mathematics and in Science. This means that the pupils have difficulty in English than in Mathematics and Science during the first quarter of the school year 2014-2015.

Considering their overall performance, the researcher shows the data reflecting the rating of 81.15% which put them in the “approaching proficiency” level.

Table 3. DUTP Performance of the Pupils in Core Subjects

Rating	Verbal Description	English		Mathematics		Science	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
85% - 89%	Proficient	12	15.00	7	8.75	2	2.50
80% - 84%	Approaching Proficiency	23	28.75	43	53.75	24	30.00
75% - 79%	Developing	45	56.25	30	37.50	54	67.50
Mean Performance μ		79.19 (Developing)		80.38 (Approaching Proficiency)		78.01 (Developing)	
Standard Deviation σ		4.12		2.96		3.05	
Overall Mean Performance				79.19 (Developing)			

The data in Table 3 reflect the DUTP performance of the pupils in the core subjects. In English, majority of the pupils (56.25%) are in the “developing” level and their overall performance is also of the same category. The researcher finds out that the same results are obtained by the pupils during the first grading period as presented in Table 2. This finding may imply that pupils have difficulty in this subject. They only acquire the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, and they need help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.

In Mathematics, majority (53.75%) of the pupils are in the “approaching proficiency” level and their overall performance is also of the same category. The same finding is obtained during the first grading period (refer to Table 2).

In Science, majority (67.50%) of the pupils are in the “developing” level and their overall performance is also of the same classification. This performance is quite low compared to what they obtained in the first grading period. This indicates that the pupils encountered difficulty in their DUTP examination in which the researcher, as part of this study, identifies the degree of difficulty of the examination. In the study of Igos, the DUTP performance of her respondents in Science is very low. Her respondents acquired a rating of 68.53% only and are classified to be in the “beginning” level (43). This just shows that pupils encountered difficulty in the DUTP examination particularly in Science.

Synthesizing the results, the researcher stresses that the pupils are in the “developing” level in English and Science as reflected in the data. It is only in Mathematics that they obtain an “approaching proficiency” level.

As to the overall DUTP performance of the pupils, they acquired a rating of 79.19% which categorized them in the “beginning” level.

The DUTP is a yearly division assessment given to the pupils to evaluate the performance of the teachers in their field. With this below average performance of the pupils, the teachers must evaluate their strategies and their efforts they put in classroom instruction.

Table 4.1 Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in English (Part 1)

English Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
14. He was _____ off his seat when he heard the shocking news. A. throw B. threw C. thrown D. thrown	35	Difficult
15. The Barangay tanods _____ the police in arresting criminals. A. has help B. have help C. has helped D. have helped	35	Difficult
16. My father _____ invitation letters on his birthday. A. has send B. had send C. has sent D. havesent	32	Difficult
18. He goes to church <u>once in a blue moon</u> ? What does the underlined phrase mean? A. once B. seldom C. sometimes D. always	38	Difficult
20. If they pass their projects, they would pass this subject. Which part of the sentence is the effect? A. they pass their projects B. their projects they would pass C. they would pass this subject D. if they pass	40	Difficult
22. Lions don't climb trees, _____? A. don't they B. does it C. do they D. are they	38	Difficult
24. Mr. Santos only earns eight thousand pesos a month. Seven hundred pesos is the _____ he can give his son for his weekly allowance. A. much B. many C. more D. most	30	Difficult

Table 4.2 Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in English (Part 2)

English Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
25. Chess is _____ to play for a <u>neophyte</u> . 26. What does the underlined word mean in number 25? A. veteran B. beginner C. champion D. loser	27	Difficult
27. Which statement below does not support the topic inside the box? <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0;"> Trees protect the lives not just of animals but also of humans. </div> A. They provide shelter for birds, monkeys, insects, and other animals. B. They hold the soil and prevent it from eroding. C. They block the sunlight and kill the smaller plants under them. D. They emit oxygen for animals and human beings to breathe.	41	Difficult

The data in Tables 4.1 and 4.2 point out some of the items in the DUTP examination in English that are classified as “difficult” or “very difficult” after the item analysis. Of the 36 items, only 9 items (25%) are identified as “difficult” items and none is categorized as “very difficult” item.

The results indicate that the pupils have difficulty in correct verb form. For example, for item number 14 “He was _____ (*throw, threw, thrown, thrown*) off his seat when he heard the shocking news”. A possible reason would be that pupils are not particular and they are confused in using the past participle form of the verb especially the irregular verbs that takes various forms. As they are usually taught the past participle, also sometimes called the passive or perfect participle, is identical to the past tense form (in -ed) in the case of regular verbs, since the **past participles for regular** verbs are the same as their past forms (look-looked-**looked** and study-studied-**studied**), for example. For irregular verbs however, the past and past participle forms are different (for example, be- was/were-**been** and go-went-**gone**).

Another item which the pupils found difficult is item number 15 which is “The Barangay tanods _____ (*has help, have help, has helped, have helped*) the police in arresting criminals.” Based on personal experience, pupils find it hard to identify the non-continuous present perfect tense which uses has or have plus the past participle and the present perfect continuous tense which uses has or have + been which is the past participle of be + the ing form of the main verb. The same with item number 16 which states “My father _____ (*has send, had send, has sent, have sent*) invitation letters on his birthday”.

Item number 18 which is “He goes to church once in a blue moon. What does the underlined phrase mean? (*once, seldom, sometimes, always*). The pupils may have taken this literally thus they missed the correct answer and since the word once have been mentioned in the selection; they took once as the correct answer.

Item number 20 which is “If they pass their projects, they would pass this subject. Which part of the sentence is the effect? (*they pass their projects, their projects they would pass, they would pass this subject, if they pass*). The word pass may have confused the pupils as it was repeatedly used in the sentence and in the choices. Based on experience pupils don’t stay long analyzing an item.

Item number 22 which is “Lions don’t climb trees, _____ ?” (*don’t they, does it, do they, are they*) A possible reason would be that the pupils lack knowledge or forget that a negative statement is followed by a positive tag question.

Item number 24 which is “*Mr. Santos only earns eight thousand pesos a month. Seven hundred pesos is the _____ (much, many, more, most) he can give his son for his weekly allowance.* A possible reason would be that the pupils missed to realize that the article *the* before the blank suggests the superlative degree. The pupils are usually taught that the words such as *of all the..., among, ever* suggest the superlative degree.

Item number 26 which is “*Chess is too difficult to play for a neophyte. (veteran, beginner, champion, loser) What does the underlined word mean?* It is evident that the pupils haven’t encountered the underlined word yet.

Item number 27 which is “*Trees protect the lives not just of animals but also of humans.*” Which statement does not support the topic? The pupils may have missed the correct answer since the choices are all in a positive form although the correct answer “*they block the sunlight and kill the smaller plants under them*” suggests a negative statement but the absence of the word “not” may have confused them.

Table 5.1 Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Mathematics (Part 1)

Mathematics Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
2. Two or more fractions whose values are equal. A. equivalent fractions B. similar fractions C. improper fractions D. fractions equal to 1	39	Difficult
5. Which part of the fraction tells the number of times the whole is being divided into? A. fraction bar B. numerator C. denominator D. none of the above	26	Difficult
6. The number used to reduce a fraction to its lowest term. A. LCD B. LCM C. GCF D. factor	28	Difficult
7. The smallest common product of two or more numbers. A. LCD B. LCM C. GCF D. product	30	Difficult
9. How do you add dissimilar fractions? A. Find the LCD of the denominators, convert the fractions to similar, and proceed to the steps in adding similar fractions. B. Find the GCF of the denominators, convert the fractions to similar, and proceed to the steps in adding similar fractions. C. Find the LCD and GCF of the denominators, convert the fractions to similar, and proceed to the steps in adding similar fractions. D. Find the GCF of the numerators and denominators, reduce to lowest term, convert the fractions to similar, and proceed to the steps in adding similar fractions.	23	Difficult

Table 5.2 Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Mathematics (Part 2)

Mathematics Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
<p>11. The number that has only one factor is 1. It is, therefore, a number.</p> <p>A. prime B. composite C. special D. odd</p>	23	Difficult
<p>15. All of these statements are true except one. Which is it?</p> <p>A. $\frac{8}{11} > \frac{5}{7}$</p> <p>B. $\frac{4}{5} < \frac{4}{5}$</p> <p>C. $\frac{5}{9} > \frac{7}{13}$</p> <p>D. $\frac{3}{8} = \frac{9}{24}$</p>	31	Difficult
<p>17. Which is a set of multiples of 8?</p> <p>A. 64, 40, 72, 88, 16, 56</p> <p>B. 8, 24, 34, 40, 80</p> <p>C. 16, 96, 32, 42, 8, 24</p> <p>D. 32, 16, 64, 76, 16</p>	34	Difficult
<p>18. What fraction is $\frac{1}{4}$ more than $\frac{2}{3}$?</p> <p>A. $\frac{5}{6}$</p> <p>B. $\frac{3}{4}$</p> <p>C. $\frac{7}{8}$</p> <p>D. $\frac{11}{12}$</p>	21	Difficult

Table 5.3
Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Mathematics (Part 3)

Mathematics Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Interpretation
<p>19. The following fractions can be renamed as terminating decimals except-----</p> <p>A. $\frac{3}{4}$</p> <p>B. $\frac{4}{5}$</p> <p>C. $\frac{5}{6}$</p> <p>D. $\frac{7}{8}$</p>	36	Difficult
<p>22. Give the prime factorization of 190.</p> <p>A. $2 \times 5 \times 19$</p> <p>B. $3 \times 5 \times 17$</p> <p>C. $1 \times 2 \times 5 \times 19$</p> <p>D. $5 \times 7 \times 23$</p>	38	Difficult
<p>23. What is the value of N in $6.96 \div N = 0.87$?</p> <p>A. 5</p> <p>B. 6</p> <p>C. 7</p> <p>D. 8</p>	31	Difficult
<p>24. If you are to reduce $117/169$ to its lowest term, what is it?</p> <p>A. $\frac{11}{15}$</p> <p>B. $\frac{9}{13}$</p> <p>C. $\frac{7}{12}$</p> <p>D. $\frac{6}{11}$</p>	31	Difficult
<p>25. What is the quotient of 3 120 divided by 0.06?</p> <p>A. 3 000</p> <p>B. 3 100</p> <p>C. 3 120</p> <p>D. 3 160</p>	25	Difficult

Table 5.4
Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Mathematics (Part 4)

Mathematics Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
28. What is the greatest common factor (GCF) of 24, 60, and 84? A. 8 B. 12 C. 6 D. 9	33	Difficult
29. Which is the list of prime factors of 160? A. 2, 5 B. 1,2,5 C. 2, 3, 5 D. 1,2,3,5	16	Difficult
30. Which statement is not true? A. $95 \div 10 = 9.5$ B. $32 \div 100 = 0.032$ C. $27 \div 1\ 000 = 0.027$ D. $50 \div 10\ 000 = 0.0050$	30	Difficult
31. Find the quotient of 1 483.20 divided by 3.6. A. 410 B. 411.2 C. 411.5 D. 412	26	Difficult
32. Which set of fractions is arranged in ascending order? A. $\frac{5}{17}, \frac{7}{12}, \frac{2}{2}, \frac{9}{8}$ B. $\frac{2}{2}, \frac{5}{17}, \frac{7}{12}, \frac{9}{8}$ C. $\frac{9}{8}, \frac{2}{2}, \frac{7}{12}, \frac{5}{17}$ D. $\frac{5}{17}, \frac{7}{12}, \frac{9}{8}, \frac{2}{2}$	13	Very Difficult
33. Jasmin bought 6 dozens of eggs for Php 360 and sold them at Php 6.50 each. How much did she gain from each egg? A. Php 2.00 B. Php 1.75 C. Php 1.50 D. Php 1.00	33	Difficult

Table 5.5
Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Mathematics (Part 5)

Mathematics Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
<p>34. Katrina gave $\frac{5}{8}$ pizza to Helen and $\frac{1}{3}$ to Rachel. How much bigger is Helen's share than Rachel's?</p> <p>A. $\frac{1}{4}$</p> <p>B. $\frac{1}{8}$</p> <p>C. $\frac{5}{24}$</p> <p>D. $\frac{7}{24}$</p>	15	Very Difficult
<p>35. Manny Pacquiao needs to spend 80.5 hours of sparring sessions this month in preparation for his next fight. If he spends 3.5 hours per session, how many sparring sessions does he need to have?</p> <p>A. 20</p> <p>B. 21</p> <p>C. 22</p> <p>D. 23</p>	33	Difficult
<p>36. To help his parents earn a living, Jamil sells old newspapers on weekends. He sold $8\frac{1}{4}$ kilograms last Saturday and $11\frac{5}{6}$ kilograms last Sunday. How many kilograms of old newspapers did he sell last weekend?</p> <p>A. $19\frac{1}{6}$</p> <p>B. $20\frac{1}{12}$</p> <p>C. $19\frac{11}{12}$</p> <p>D. $20\frac{3}{4}$</p>	18	Difficult

The data in Tables 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5 reflect some of the items in the DUTP examination in Mathematics that are classified as “difficult” or “very difficult” after the item analysis. Of the 36 items, 21 items (58.33%) are identified as “difficult” and only 2 (5.56%) items are categorized as “very difficult”.

The findings indicate that the pupils have difficulty in recalling the mathematical terminologies like the following: equivalent fractions, denominator, multiples of a number, prime factorization, terminating decimals, LCD, LCM, GCF, prime number, composite number and some other basic but important terms. Obtaining no ability to remember these terminologies will result to difficulty in performing its operation. They also find it hard to compare and reduce or simplify fractions. Furthermore, arranging numbers and solving worded problems that involve fractions are noted to be “very difficult” to the pupils.

The item analysis also reveals that difficulty is observed in problems that involve the following: division of decimals and ratio and proportion with decimal numbers.

Bohol in her study revealed the following operations in fractions as “moderately” difficult as perceived by her respondents: determining whether the fraction is in its lowest terms or not, dividing of fractions, adding and subtracting mixed fractions with different denominators, and multiplying and dividing mixed fractions (36-37). Based on the results of the examination given to the respondents, the study was revealed that their performance in division of fractions is in the “developing” (79.18%) level and “beginning” (74.19%) level in operations on mixed fractions (39).

Guiler’s findings indicated that the percentage of pupils exhibiting weakness in division of fractions and mixed numbers almost double the percentage of those exhibiting weakness in addition (146-156). As cited by Bruce and Ross, educators and researchers agree that most students encounter significant problems and misconceptions when learning fractions (cited in Bohol 16). According to Hasemann, children find fractions so challenging because there are many rules associated with the procedures of fractions, and these rules are more complex than those of natural numbers (71-87).

Table 6.1
Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Science (Part 1)

Science Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
1. If a customer complains about the drinking water characteristics, the operator should record the complaint and _____ A. Investigate immediately B. Investigate only if more complaints are received. C. Inform the customer that the water should be boiled. D. Inform the customer that the water is safe.	31	Difficult
What gas prevents warm air from escaping? A. oxygen B. nitrogen C. carbon dioxide D. phosphorous	39	Difficult
15. A toy robot can talk and walk and run on batteries. What type of energy is stored in the batteries? A. chemical B. kinetic C. nuclear D. thermal	39	Difficult
Which of the following represents a chemical reaction? A. sugar cube dissolving in water B. ice cubes forming in a freezer C. ice cream melting in a freezer D. cake baking in an oven	21	Difficult
Which best describes a parallel circuit? A. Electricity flows along one pathway. B. The flow of electricity comes from one source. C. Electricity flows along more than one pathway. D. The flow of electricity comes from more than one source.	30	Difficult
19. When heat from a stove is used to boil water in a saucepan, this is an example of _____ A. energy transfer B. friction C. transformation of energy D. conservation of energy	38	Difficult

Table 6.2
Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Science (Part 2)

Science Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
20-23. Name a gadget where the following transformation of energies take place. the gadgets inside the box. <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; display: inline-block; margin: 10px 0;"> Loud Sneaker Electric fan Electric bulb </div>		
20. Chemical energy to electrical energy-_____	21	Difficult
Electrical energy to mechanical energy-_____	34	Difficult
Electrical energy to heat and light-_____	28	Difficult
25. Which one of these is not a problem associated with an overpopulated country? A. Lack of workers to exploit the country’s natural resources B. Overcrowded cities C. Lack of suitable housing D. High unemployment or underemployment rates	37	Difficult
27. A small amount of soil, a hydrilla plant and a fish were placed in a large bottle. The bottle was sealed to prevent the exchange of gases and other materials between its contents and the outside. The bottle was placed in a window to receive light during the daytime. Is photosynthesis produced by the plants? A. Yes, because the elements for photosynthesis are available B. No, it is not produced because the bottle was sealed C. Yes, photosynthesis is produced during night time only. D. No, plants take in only the waste products exhaled by animals.	41	Difficult
28. “Energy cannot be created nor destroyed in any chemical reaction. It can only be changed from one form to another”. This is known as the Law of: A. Law of Energy Transfer B. Law of Conservation of Energy C. Law of Energy Transformation	31	Difficult
Law of Thermodynamics Which of the following animals might compete with the rat in this food chain? 	31	Difficult
A. chicken B. carabao C. dog D. cat		

Table 6.3
Index of Difficulty of DUTP Examination in Science (Part 3)

Science Items	Index of Difficulty (%)	Inter-pretation
Which of the following objects has kinetic energy? A. bicycle parked at the top of a hill B. leaves lying on the ground beneath a tree C. a ball rolling across the floor D. a sunny windowsill	30	Difficult
32. Why are watering plants and grass in the early morning a way to conserve water? A. There is always more water in the morning. B. Smaller amounts of water evaporate in the cool morning. C. Water used in the morning can be recycled for afternoon use. D. Grass can absorb water only in the morning.	28	Difficult

The data in Tables 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3 indicate some of the items in the DUTP examination in Science that are classified as “difficult” or “very difficult” after the item analysis. Of the 36 items, only 16 items (44.44%) are identified as “difficult” items and none is categorized as “very difficult” item.

The results indicate that the pupils lack knowledge on the scientific method as observed in test item number 1. They also find it hard to point out the type of energy as evident in numbers 1, 16 and 19. Pupils also show difficulty in knowing the different transformations of energies that take place. Furthermore, they also show their lack of understanding in the questions as evident in numbers 25 and 27 which result to poor choices of answers.

The item analysis also reveals that difficulty is observed in knowing a simple electromagnet, basic forms of energy as well as the three laws of energy. Moreover, the pupils also show difficulty in the relationship of the food chain.

Table 7
Relationship between the First Grading and DUTP Performance of the Pupils in the Core Subjects

Variables	Computed r	Degree of Relationship
First Grading Grade in English and DUTP Examination Result in English	0.7723	High
First Grading Grade in Mathematics and DUTP Examination Result in Mathematics	0.4399	Marked
First Grading Grade in Science and DUTP Examination Result in Science	0.6610	High

The data in Table 7 indicate that there is a “high” relationship between the first grading grade and DUTP performance of the pupils in English. This means that their first grading performance is considered as a predictor on their performance in the DUTP examination. The same degree of relationship is noted between the first grading and DUTP performance of the pupils in Science. While in Mathematics, the relationship is classified as “marked”. The results imply that pupils with higher performance during the first grading period are likely to obtain higher performance also in the DUTP examination. Similarly, those who obtain lower performance in the first grading period have also lower performance in the DUTP examination.

Prior knowledge has a large influence on student performance, explaining up to 81% of the variance in posttest scores (Dochy, Segers, and Buehl). There is also a well-established correlation between prior knowledge and reading comprehension (Langer, et al.). In addition, high correlations have been found between prior knowledge and speed and accuracy of study behavior (cited in Dochy et al.). Thus, prior knowledge is associated with beneficial academic behaviors and higher academic performance.

Table 8
Difference in Performance of the Male and Female Pupils

Sex	English		Mathematics		Science	
	Mean μ	Verbal Equivalent	Mean μ	Verbal Equivalent	Mean μ	Verbal Equivalent
First Grading Period Performance						
Male	76.97	Developing	81.97	Approaching Proficiency	79.83	Approaching Proficiency
Female	80.00	Approaching Proficiency	82.67	Approaching Proficiency	84.50	Proficient
DUTP Performance						
Male	77.69	Developing	79.97	Approaching Proficiency	77.40	Developing
Female	80.36	Approaching Proficiency	80.69	Approaching Proficiency	78.49	Developing

The data in Table 8 reflect that in the first grading performance of the pupils in English, the male pupils are classified to be in the “developing” (76.97%) level while the female are categorized to be in the “approaching proficiency” (80.00%) level. The same classification is noted considering the DUTP performance of the pupils. The male pupils obtained a “developing” (77.69%) level description while the female pupils garnered an “approaching proficiency” (80.36%) level category.

There is a substantial difference in the performance of the girls and boys in English with girls doing better than boys by 14.6 percent. (“Girls Beat Boys Again in GCSE Battle”).

Standardized achievement tests also show that females are better at spelling and perform better on tests of literacy, writing, and general knowledge (National Center for Education Statistics). An international aptitude test administered to fourth graders in 35 countries, for example, showed that females outscored males on reading literacy in every country.

In late elementary school, females outperform males on several verbal skills tasks: verbal reasoning, verbal fluency, comprehension, and understanding logical relations (“Gender and Academic Achievement”).

Considering the Mathematics performance of the pupils during the first grading, the researcher shows that male and female pupils are identified to be in the “approaching proficiency” level. They have a rating of 81.97% and 82.67%, respectively. The same classification is noted considering their DUTP performance. The male pupils obtain a rating of 79.97% and the female pupils obtain a rating of 80.69%. These ratings are classified to be in the “approaching proficiency” level. The researcher would like to emphasize that the numerical ratings of the two groups of pupils become lower in the DUTP examination but they have the same description. With these results, one can deduce that male and female pupils have the same performance in Mathematics and the numerical decrease of their ratings may be due to the difficulty of the DUTP examination given to them. As reflected in Tables 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, of the 36 items, 21 items (58.33%) are identified as “difficult” and 2 (5.56%) items are categorized as “very difficult”.

Males and females do equally well in basic math knowledge (“Gender and Academic Achievement”). The mathematical skills of boys and girls, as well as of men and women, are substantially equal according to a new examination of existing studies in the current online edition of journal Psychological Bulletin (“Large Study Shows Females are Equal to Males in Math Skills”).

There was no gender difference in understanding of mathematical concepts at any age. For complex problem solving, there was no gender difference in elementary or middle school. Findings from a recent analysis of data from state assessments of mathematics performance provide evidence that the gender gap in mathematics performance in the U.S. has indeed diminished or even vanished (Hyde, Lindberg, Linn, Ellis, and Williams).

In Science, the table presents that male pupils are in the “approaching proficiency” (79.83%) level and female pupils are in the “proficient” (84.50%) level in the first grading period. This finding suggests that female pupils are better than male pupils in Science during the first grading period. However, concerning their DUTP performance, the finding shows that male and female pupils are classified to be in the “developing” level. The former garnered a rating of 77.40% while the latter obtained a rating of 78.49%. The finding also indicates that the performance of the two groups of pupils becomes lower in the DUTP examination. The researcher thought that the pupils may find the examination in Science hard as revealed in Tables 6.1 and 6.2 wherein 44.44% of the items are identified to be difficult. Thus, the performances of the two groups of pupils are affected.

The Wellcome Trust Monitor also reported that around 40 per cent of young people put off learning science because they find the subject difficult or boring (Butt et al.). This was echoed in the other research by Oversby in 2005 and by Williams et al. in 2003 who noted that half of the students answering their questionnaires found physics either ‘boring’ or ‘very boring’. Furthermore, Williams et al. found there was a link between finding a subject boring and perceiving it as difficult.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

From the findings above, the following conclusions are made:

1. Majority of the pupils are female.
2. The pupils' first grading period performance in English is in the "developing" level and in the "approaching proficiency" level for both Science and Mathematics.
3. The pupils' DUTP performance in English and Science is in the "developing" level and in the "approaching proficiency" level in Mathematics.
4. The following proportions of items in the DUTP examinations are found to be difficult: one-fourth of the items in English, more than half of the items in Mathematics, and almost half of the items in Science.
5. There is a "high" relationship between the first grading and DUTP performance of the pupils in English as well as in Science. A "marked" relationship is also noted in Mathematics.
6. A substantial difference is revealed between the performance of the male and female pupils in the following areas: English and Science in the first grading period; and English in the DUTP examination in favor of the female pupils.

In general, the DUTP performance of the pupils in the core subjects is in the "developing level". In terms of index of difficulty, one-fourth of the items in English, almost one-half of the items in Science and more than one-half of the items in Mathematics are classified as difficult.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings of this study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Since the pupils are in the "developing" level in English (both in the first grading period and DUTP performance), the teachers should consider the item analysis results. Items that are considered difficult should be stressed more in classroom discussion.
2. Inasmuch as there were numerous difficult items in Mathematics and Science for the pupils during the DUTP examination, a well-planned tutorial session should be organized by the teachers. This activity should be done a month before the said examination.
3. The male pupils should be encouraged to participate more in classroom discussion. During class activities, they should be paired with female pupils who excel in class.
4. The supervisors should ensure that the items included in the DUTP examination go through an item analysis.

PROGRAM DESIGN

Proposed Program for Improving Pupils' DUTP Performance

I. Program Title : Activities Designed for DUTP Evaluation

II. Proponent : Eden Joy F. Gantalao

III. Target Users : Banaybanay E/S Grade-VI

IV. Background and Rationale:

It has been revealed that several items in the DUTP examination are classified as difficult to the pupils. In English, one-fourth of the items are identified as difficult. In Mathematics, more than half of the items are also categorized as difficult. Moreover, in Science almost half of the items are labeled as difficult. In addition their performance in these core subjects especially in English and Science are poor. Hence, this program is designed to improve classroom instruction and to improve pupils' performance.

V. Project Objectives

This program aims to increase the DUTP performance of the pupils in English, Mathematics, and Science.

Specifically, it aims to:

1. help the pupils in their difficulty in some specific areas in English like subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, correct verb form, idiomatic expressions, vocabulary, and reading comprehension;
2. provide assistance to the pupils in their difficulty in Mathematics especially in recalling the mathematical terminologies; comparing and reducing or simplifying fractions; arranging numbers; solving worded problems that involve fractions; division of decimals and ratio and proportion with decimal numbers; and
3. aid pupils in their difficulty in Science especially in the scientific method; types of energy; transformation of energies; electromagnet process, basic forms and laws of energy; relationship of the food chain and poor understanding of the questions.

A Proposed Program for Improving Pupils' DUTP Performance

Areas Of Concern	Objectives	Activities	People Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicators
English					
Pupils' poor performance in subject verb agreement	To provide the pupils with activities that will enhance their performance	Drills Peer Tutorials Oral Reading Writing Exercises Group Work Working by Pairs	English teachers, tutors, other volunteers, and grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved performance in subject verb agreement
Pupils' poor performance in correct tenses	To help the pupils improve their ability to use appropriate verb tenses	Drills Activities on the correct verb forms Oral and Silent Reading of pre-selected reading materials Writing Exercises	English teachers, tutors, other volunteers, and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved performance in correct tenses
Pupils' poor performance in correct verb form	To guide the pupils in performing activities that will improve their use of correct verb forms	Role playing Oral Recitation Question and Answer Interviewing	English teachers, tutors, other volunteers, and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved performance in correct verb forms
Pupils' poor performance in the use of idiomatic expressions	To make the students aware of the importance of idiomatic expressions	Listening activities Introduce the pupils to idiomatic expressions using idiomatic expressions Oral reading focusing on idiomatic expressions	English teachers, tutor, other volunteers and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved performance in the use of idiomatic expressions
Pupils' poor performance in vocabulary	To encourage the pupils to improve their vocabulary	Various reading activities Word drills Activities on unlocking difficult words	English teachers, tutors, other volunteers, and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved performance in vocabulary
Pupils' poor performance in reading comprehension	To help pupils improve their reading comprehension ability	Oral and silent reading focusing on reading comprehension	English teachers, tutors, and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improve pupils' performance in reading comprehension

Areas Of Concern	Objectives	Activities	People Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicators
Mathematics					
Pupils poor performance in comparing and reducing or simplifying fractions	To improve the skills of the pupils in comparing and reducing or simplifying fractions by providing different strategies.	Drills and activities comparing and reducing or simplifying fractions	Math teachers, peer tutors, and the grade VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improve skills in comparing and reducing or simplifying fractions
Pupils' poor performance in arranging fractional numbers	To guide pupils in arranging fractional numbers by introducing different methods	Skip counting drill games on arranging fractional numbers	Math teachers, peer tutors, and the grade VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improve pupils' skills in arranging numbers
Pupils poor performance solving worded problems that involve fractions	To help pupils' improve their performance in solving worded problems that involve fractions	Problem solving activities, worksheets	Math teachers, peer tutors, and the grade VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	improve pupils' performance in solving worded problems that involve fractions
Pupils' poor performance in division of decimals and ratio and proportion with decimal numbers	To guide the pupils in improving their performance in division of decimals, ratio and proportion with decimal numbers	Drills, activities on decimal place value	Math teachers, peer tutors, and the grade VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improve performance in division of decimals and ratio and proportion with decimal numbers

Areas Of Concern	Objectives	Activities	People Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicators
Science					
Pupils' poor performance in knowing the scientific method	To provide the pupils activities that will enhance their knowledge on the scientific method	Reflective analysis, learning cycle lesson activities relating to tackling scientific method	Science teachers, peer tutors, other volunteers and grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved pupils' knowledge in knowing the scientific method
Pupils' difficulty in knowing the types of energy	To help the pupils improve their ability in knowing types of energy	Open-ended questions, follow-up reflective analysis	Science teachers, peer tutors, other volunteers and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved pupils' knowledge on the types of energy
Pupils' poor knowledge on transformation of energy	To guide the pupils in performing activities that will improve their knowledge on the transformation of energy	Oral presentation, group presentation, simulation, role play	Science teachers, peer tutors, other volunteers and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved pupils' knowledge on transformation of energies
Pupils' difficulty in knowing simple electromagnet	To make the pupils aware of the importance of the simple electromagnet	Conducts experiments, research report	Science teachers, peer tutor, other volunteers and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved pupils' knowledge on simple electromagnet
Pupils' difficulty in knowing the laws of energy	To encourage the pupils to improve knowledge on laws of energy	Oral presentation	English teachers, peer tutors, other volunteers and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improved pupils' knowledge on the laws of energy
Pupils' poor knowledge on the relationship of the food chain	To help pupils improve their knowledge on the relationship of the food chain	Sharing of results with peers, oral presentation	Science teachers, peer tutors, and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improve pupils' knowledge on the relationship of the food chain
Pupils' poor understanding of the questions and Science terminologies	To help pupils improve their reading comprehension ability	Oral and silent reading focusing on comprehension and simple terminologies in Science	Science teachers, peer tutors, and the grade-VI pupils	School year 2015-2016	Improve pupils' performance in reading comprehension in Science

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